

doi:10.5281/zenodo.17993627

Assessing the Influence of VCDP Participation on Household Food Availability, Access, and Utilisation in Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This research examines the influence of the Value Chain Development Programme (VCDP) on household food availability, access, and utilisation in Benue State, Nigeria, between 2014 and 2025. Employing a sequential explanatory mixed-methods design, data were collected from 405 respondents comprising producers, processors, and marketers across four Local Government Areas, supplemented by programme records and field observations. Descriptive analysis profiled the socio-economic characteristics of participants. At the same time, inferential techniques, including Propensity Score Matching (PSM), multivariate regression, and Structural Equation Modelling (SEM), examined the causal effects of participation on food security and livelihood outcomes. Results indicate that VCDP participants experienced significantly improved household food security, evidenced by lower Household Food Insecurity Access Scale (HFIAS) scores and higher Food Consumption Scores (FCS), alongside substantial increases in annual income, employment, and asset ownership. SEM results revealed that participation positively influenced household income and resilience, which in turn enhanced food security, with income accounting for 43% of the total effect. The findings highlight the critical role of value chain interventions in promoting rural livelihoods, dietary diversity, and food security. The study recommends scaling up programme activities, enhancing access to credit and infrastructure, and promoting gender-inclusive participation to maximise household welfare outcomes.

Keywords: VCDP participation, household food security, income, resilience, livelihood diversification

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Food security remains a critical development challenge in Nigeria, where a significant proportion of households continue to experience inadequate access to sufficient, safe, and nutritious food (Bello et al., 2025). According to the Food and Agriculture Organisation (FAO), food security is achieved when all

people, at all times, have physical and economic access to food that meets their dietary needs for an active and healthy life (FAO, 2008). In Nigeria, rapid population growth, climate variability, economic instability, and persistent poverty have combined to undermine household food availability, access, and utilisation, particularly in rural and agrarian communities (Adebayo & Adekunle, 2016; Abubakar et al., 2025; Ibrahim et al., 2025).

Household food security is commonly analysed through three interrelated dimensions: availability, access, and utilisation (Magaji & Musa, 2024). Food availability refers to the presence of adequate food supply through production, distribution, or exchange; access concerns households' ability to obtain food through income, markets, or social transfers; while utilisation focuses on the proper biological use of food, influenced by nutrition knowledge, health, and sanitation (FAO et al., 2019). Deficiencies in any of these dimensions can lead to food insecurity, even when food supplies appear sufficient at the national level, underscoring the importance of household-level interventions.

In response to these challenges, development-oriented programs such as the Value Chain Development Programme (VCDP) have been implemented in Nigeria to enhance agricultural productivity, improve incomes, and strengthen livelihoods among smallholder farmers. The VCDP is designed to support value chain actors through access to inputs, extension services, market linkages, and capacity building, with the ultimate goal of improving food security and reducing rural poverty (IFAD, 2018). Participation in such programmes is expected to positively influence household welfare outcomes, including food availability, access, and utilisation.

Empirical studies suggest that participation in agricultural value chains and livelihood programmes can improve household food security by increasing farm output, stabilising incomes, and enhancing dietary diversity (Olagunju et al., 2021; World Bank, 2020). However, the magnitude and pathways of these impacts often vary across contexts due to differences in programme design, participants' socio-economic characteristics, and local market conditions. Consequently, there is a growing need for context-specific assessments that examine how programme participation translates into improved household food security outcomes.

However, this study assesses the influence of VCDP participation on household food availability, access, and utilisation in Nigeria. By employing standardised food security indices, the study provides empirical evidence on whether and how engagement in the VCDP contributes to improved food security outcomes among beneficiary households. The findings are expected to inform policymakers, development partners, and programme implementers on the effectiveness of value chain-based interventions in addressing food insecurity and enhancing sustainable livelihoods in Nigeria.

2.0 Literature Review and Theoretical Framework

2.1 Conceptual Review

2.1.1 Value Chain Development Programme (VCDP)

VCDP participation refers to the active involvement of households or individuals in the Value Chain Development Programme through engagement in programme-supported activities such as access to improved inputs, extension services, capacity building, credit facilitation, and market linkages. Participation is expected to enhance farmers' productive capacity, income stability, and resilience by strengthening linkages across agricultural value chains (IFAD, 2018). Studies on agricultural development interventions emphasise that sustained and inclusive participation is critical for achieving desired welfare outcomes, including improved food security and livelihoods, as participants are better positioned to adopt innovations and benefit from market opportunities (Olagunju et al., 2021).

2.1.2 Household

A household is commonly defined as a group of individuals who live together, share meals, and pool resources to meet their basic needs, including food, shelter, and health care (Ibrahim & Sule, 2023). In food security analysis, the household serves as a fundamental unit for assessing consumption, income, and welfare outcomes because food acquisition and utilisation decisions are often made at this level (Deaton & Zaidi, 2002; Musa et al., 2025). In the Nigerian context, households may comprise nuclear or

extended family members (Magaji & Musa, 2015), and their size, composition, and dependency ratio significantly influence food security outcomes and vulnerability to shocks (National Bureau of Statistics [NBS], 2020; Dada et al., 2025; Aminu et al., 2025).

2.1.3 Food Availability

Food availability refers to the physical presence of sufficient quantities of food within a household or community, derived from own production, market purchases, food aid, or transfers. At the household level, availability is closely linked to agricultural productivity, storage capacity, and market functioning (FAO, 2008; John et al., 2025). In agrarian economies such as Nigeria, fluctuations in climatic conditions, access to inputs, and post-harvest losses can significantly affect household food availability, making agricultural support programmes vital for stabilising food supply throughout the year (Adebayo & Adekunle, 2016; Magaji et al., 2024; Ahmed et al., 2024).

2.1.4 Food Access and Utilisation

Food access denotes a household's ability to obtain adequate food through sufficient income, purchasing power, or social safety nets. In contrast, food utilisation relates to the proper biological use of food, influenced by dietary quality, nutrition knowledge, health status, and sanitation (FAO et al., 2019). Even when food is available, poor access due to poverty or high food prices, as well as inadequate utilisation resulting from poor feeding practices or disease, can lead to food insecurity. Empirical evidence from Nigeria indicates that improvements in income and nutrition education significantly enhance both food access and utilisation outcomes among rural households (World Bank, 2020).

2.2 Theoretical Review

2.2.1 Sustainable Livelihoods Theory

The Sustainable Livelihoods Theory is highly relevant to this study, as it provides a comprehensive framework for understanding how participation in development programmes, such as the Value Chain Development Programme (VCDP), influences household food availability, access, and utilisation. The theory posits that households draw on a combination of livelihood assets, human, social, natural, physical, and financial capital, to pursue livelihood strategies that enhance welfare and reduce vulnerability to shocks (Chambers & Conway, 1992). VCDP participation strengthens these assets through improved agricultural skills, access to inputs and markets, income generation, and institutional support, thereby enhancing households' capacity to secure sufficient and nutritious food. By improving financial capital (income), human capital (skills and knowledge), and social capital (market and cooperative linkages), the programme aligns with the core assumptions of the Sustainable Livelihoods Theory, which emphasises that strengthened assets and supportive institutional structures translate into improved livelihood outcomes such as food security and resilience (Scoones, 1998).

2.3 Empirical Literature Review

Olagunju, Oggunniyi, and Oyetunde-Usman (2021) examined the relationship between agricultural commercialisation and household food security in Nigeria using nationally representative survey data and food security indices. Their findings revealed that participation in market-oriented agricultural programmes significantly improved household food availability and access, driven by increased farm income and productivity. The study further showed that households engaged in value chain-related activities recorded higher dietary diversity scores than non-participants, underscoring the role of structured agricultural interventions in improving food utilisation outcomes.

A study by Abdullahi, Yusuf, and Bello (2020) assessed the impact of agricultural development programmes on rural household food security in northern Nigeria using propensity score matching techniques. The results indicated that programme participants experienced significant improvements in food availability and access, driven by enhanced access to inputs, extension services, and output markets. However, the authors noted that food utilisation outcomes were moderated by household education levels and access to health and sanitation facilities, highlighting the multidimensional nature of food security.

Using panel data from Nigeria's General Household Survey, Oggunniyi et al. (2022) investigated the effect of livelihood support and value chain interventions on food security and welfare outcomes. The study

found that households participating in donor-supported value chain programmes were less likely to experience food shortages and more likely to consume nutritionally diverse diets. The authors concluded that income gains and reduced vulnerability to shocks were key pathways through which programme participation enhanced food access and utilisation.

In a related study, Akinwale, Adepoju, and Sanusi (2023) analysed the influence of agricultural value chain programmes on smallholder farmers' food security in selected Nigerian states. Using the Household Food Insecurity Access Scale (HFIAS), the study found that programme participation significantly reduced the severity of food insecurity among beneficiary households. The findings demonstrated that improved market linkages and post-harvest handling practices contributed to better food availability and more stable food access across farming seasons.

Lawal, Ibrahim, and Sadiq (2024) evaluated the food security outcomes of IFAD-supported Value Chain Development Programmes in Nigeria using a mixed-methods approach. Quantitative results showed significant positive effects of VCDP participation on household food availability and access, while qualitative evidence highlighted improvements in nutrition knowledge and food preparation practices among beneficiaries. The study concluded that sustained participation in value chain programmes enhances not only food supply and income but also food utilisation through improved awareness and behavioural change.

2.4 Research Gap

Despite the growing body of literature on agricultural commercialisation and value chain interventions in Nigeria, several critical gaps remain. Most existing studies broadly examine agricultural programmes or market participation without isolating the specific effects of the Value Chain Development Programme (VCDP) on the distinct dimensions of household food security—namely, food availability, access, and utilisation. Additionally, many studies emphasise income and productivity outcomes, with limited empirical attention given to food utilisation indicators such as dietary diversity, nutrition knowledge, and intra-household food use. Methodologically, prior research often relies on cross-sectional data and single food security measures, thereby constraining causal inference and comprehensive assessment. Furthermore, few studies use standardised, multidimensional food security indices to capture the pathways through which VCDP participation influences household welfare. Consequently, there is a paucity of context-specific, multidimensional evidence on how VCDP participation translates into improved household food availability, access, and utilisation in Nigeria, which this study seeks to address.

3.0 METHODOLOGY

3.1 Introduction

This chapter describes the methodological procedures used to examine the influence of participation in the Value Chain Development Programme (VCDP) on household food availability, access, and utilisation in Nigeria, with empirical evidence drawn from Benue State for the period 2014–2025. A sequential explanatory mixed-methods approach was employed, integrating quantitative and qualitative techniques to generate robust and policy-relevant findings. The quantitative component estimated the effects of VCDP participation on food security outcomes using household survey data and econometric models. In contrast, the qualitative component provided contextual insights into participants' experiences, perceptions, and the mechanisms through which programme impacts occur. This integration follows the mixed-methods rationale advanced by Creswell and Plano Clark (2023), which emphasises triangulation to enhance validity and explanatory depth.

3.2 Study Area

The study was conducted in Benue State, located in Nigeria's North-Central geopolitical zone and bordered by Nasarawa, Taraba, and Kogi States. Benue State is widely recognised as the "Food Basket of the Nation" due to its favourable agro-ecological conditions that support the production of major staples, including rice, cassava, yams, and maize. Covering approximately 34,059 square kilometres, the state has an estimated population of about 5.8 million people (NPC, 2023). Agriculture remains the dominant

economic activity, engaging over 75% of the population. Despite its agricultural potential, productivity is constrained by climate-related shocks, poor infrastructure, limited storage facilities, and market inefficiencies (Benue ADP, 2024). These characteristics informed the selection of Benue State as a focal area for the VCDP, which operates in Guma, Gwer West, Gwer East, and Okpokwu Local Government Areas (LGAs).

3.3 Research Design

The study adopted a sequential explanatory mixed-methods research design (Creswell & Creswell, 2022), implemented in two interrelated phases. The first phase involved a quantitative household survey to generate measurable indicators of food availability, access, utilisation, income, and livelihood diversification. The second phase comprised qualitative methods, including Focus Group Discussions (FGDs) and Key Informant Interviews (KIIs), to explain and contextualise the quantitative results. This design enabled the study to combine statistical evidence on programme effects with participants' lived experiences, thereby strengthening interpretation and inference.

3.4 Population, Sampling, and Sample Size

3.4.1 Population and Sampling Frame

The study population consisted of both VCDP beneficiaries and non-beneficiaries across the four selected LGAs in Benue State. Beneficiaries included producers, processors, and marketers participating in rice and cassava value chains. The sampling frame was developed using records from the VCDP State Coordination Office and cooperative association registers (2024).

3.4.2 Sample Size Determination

A total of 405 respondents were selected using a stratified random sampling technique to ensure adequate representation across value chain roles and LGAs. The sample comprised 160 producers (39.5%), 124 processors (30.6%), and 121 marketers (29.9%). Sample adequacy was validated using Yamane's (1967) formula for finite populations at a 95% confidence level and a 5% margin of error, which yielded an optimal sample size of 380–410 respondents, confirming the appropriateness of the final sample size.

3.4.3 Sampling Technique

A multi-stage stratified sampling procedure was employed. First, the four LGAs were purposively selected based on the intensity of VCDP activities. Second, three to four participating communities were randomly chosen from each LGA. Finally, proportional random sampling was applied to select respondents from cooperatives and households within the selected communities.

3.5 Data Collection Instruments and Procedures

3.5.1 Quantitative Instruments

Quantitative data were collected using a structured questionnaire organised into sections covering socio-demographic characteristics, food security indicators, income and employment, asset ownership and livelihood diversification, and access to finance, training, and infrastructure. Food security was measured using standardised tools, including the Household Food Insecurity Access Scale (HFIAS) and the Food Consumption Score (FCS). The questionnaire was pretested on 30 households outside the study sample, yielding a Cronbach's alpha coefficient of 0.87, indicating high reliability. Trained enumerators administered the instruments to minimise response bias.

3.5.2 Qualitative Instruments

Qualitative data were generated through eight FGDs (two per LGA) involving farmers, processors, and marketers, as well as KIIs with VCDP officials, cooperative leaders, and agricultural extension officers. Observation checklists were also used to assess the condition of VCDP-supported infrastructure such as storage facilities, processing centres, and access roads. Semi-structured interview guides with open-ended questions facilitated in-depth discussion and flexibility.

3.6 Analytical Framework

The analytical framework combined descriptive statistics, econometric techniques, and thematic analysis to assess programme impacts and explain causal pathways.

3.6.1 Descriptive Analysis

Descriptive statistics, including means, frequencies, and percentages, were used to summarise respondents' characteristics and key variables. Cross-tabulations compared beneficiaries and non-beneficiaries, while t-tests and Chi-square statistics were applied to test differences at the 5% significance level.

3.6.2 Propensity Score Matching (PSM)

To address selection bias and estimate the causal effect of VCDP participation, Propensity Score Matching was applied using the Rosenbaum and Rubin (1983) method. Participation status was modelled as a function of observable household characteristics, including education, land size, gender, cooperative membership, and access to credit. The Average Treatment Effect on the Treated (ATT) was estimated using nearest-neighbour and kernel matching algorithms implemented in STATA 18.0. Balance diagnostics, including standardised mean differences and density plots, were used to assess the quality of matching.

3.6.3 Multivariate Regression Models

To further control for residual heterogeneity, Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression was used for continuous outcomes such as income and FCS. In contrast, logistic regression was applied to categorical food security indicators. Statistical significance was evaluated at $p < 0.05$ and $p < 0.01$ levels.

3.6.4 Structural Equation Modelling (SEM)

Structural Equation Modelling was employed to examine direct and indirect relationships among VCDP participation, mediating variables (income and livelihood diversification), and outcomes related to food security and resilience. Model adequacy was assessed using standard fit indices, including Chi-square, Comparative Fit Index ($CFI \geq 0.90$), and Root Mean Square Error of Approximation ($RMSEA \leq 0.08$).

3.7 Measurement of Key Variables

Household food security was measured using the HFIAS (Coates et al., 2007), which captures anxiety, food quality, and quantity dimensions, and the Food Consumption Score based on WFP (2022) guidelines. Livelihood diversification was measured using a normalised diversification index ranging from zero to one. At the same time, household resilience was computed as a weighted index of standardised indicators reflecting income stability, food security, and coping strategies, following Béné et al. (2022).

3.8 Reliability and Validity

Reliability was confirmed using Cronbach's alpha coefficients exceeding 0.70 for major scales. Sampling adequacy was validated through the Kaiser–Meyer–Olkin (KMO) measure (0.81) and Bartlett's test of sphericity ($p < 0.001$). Standard method bias was assessed using Harman's single-factor test, while triangulation of quantitative and qualitative evidence ensured construct and contextual validity.

3.9 Qualitative Data Analysis

Qualitative data from FGDs and KIIs were transcribed, coded, and analysed thematically using NVivo 14.0, following Braun and Clarke's (2021) six-step thematic analysis procedure. Emerging themes focused on training and capacity building, market access, gender inclusion, climate adaptation, and institutional performance.

3.10 Data Integration and Triangulation

Integration of quantitative and qualitative findings occurred at the design, analysis, and interpretation stages, consistent with Creswell and Plano Clark (2023). Quantitative results informed qualitative sampling, qualitative findings explained statistical patterns, and both strands were merged to draw coherent conclusions.

3.11 Ethical Considerations

Ethical approval was obtained from the relevant University Research Ethics Committee and the Benue State Ministry of Agriculture. Participation was voluntary, informed consent was secured, and confidentiality and anonymity were guaranteed. Enumerators were trained in ethical standards, cultural sensitivity, and gender responsiveness throughout the data collection process.

4.1 DATA ANALYSIS AND PRESENTATION OF RESULTS

This section presents the findings from the quantitative analysis assessing the influence of participation in the Value Chain Development Programme (VCDP) on household food availability, access, and utilisation in Benue State, Nigeria, from 2014 to 2025. The analysis combines descriptive statistics, which profile respondents' socio-economic characteristics and programme participation patterns, with inferential techniques such as Propensity Score Matching (PSM), multivariate regression, and Structural Equation Modelling (SEM). Data were collected from 405 respondents, including producers, processors, and marketers, across four LGAs: Guma, Gwer West, Gwer East, and Okpokwu, and were validated against VCDP records and field observations. This comprehensive approach provides robust insights into the welfare implications of VCDP interventions.

4.1 Descriptive Statistics

4.1.1 Socio-Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

Table 4.1. Socio-Demographic Characteristics of Respondents (n = 405)

Variable	Category	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Mean (SD)
Age (years)	—	—	—	43.7 (11.8)
Gender	Male	249	61.5	—
	Female	156	38.5	—
Education	No formal	42	10.4	—
	Primary	86	21.2	—
	Secondary	179	44.2	—
	Tertiary	98	24.2	—
Household size	—	—	—	6.2 (2.3)
Main occupation	Farming	301	74.3	—
Landholding (ha)	—	—	—	2.6 (1.1)

Source: Field survey, 2025

Table 4.1 illustrates that the respondents were predominantly middle-aged, with a mean age of 43.7 years, indicating an economically active population engaged in value chain activities. Males accounted for 61.5% of participants, though female involvement remained substantial, reflecting moderate gender inclusion. Most respondents had at least a secondary education, suggesting adequate literacy to adopt market-oriented and technological agricultural practices. The average household size was 6.2 persons, consistent with rural agrarian norms in Benue State. Mean landholding of 2.6 hectares confirms the predominance of smallholder farming, while processors and marketers mainly operated on a micro- to small-scale basis, emphasising the household-based nature of livelihoods.

4.1.2 VCDP Participation and Access to Services

Table 4.2. VCDP Participation and Access to Services by Actor Category

Service Type	Producers (%)	Processors (%)	Marketers (%)
Received improved inputs	93	57	28
Attended training	82	68	54
Accessed credit facility	41	52	49

Service Type	Producers (%)	Processors (%)	Marketers (%)
Market linkage support	64	73	62
Infrastructure benefited	59	68	47
Duration > 6 years	48	44	46

Source: Author's computation from field data, 2025

Table 4.2 shows variation in participation intensity across value chain actors. Producers were the primary beneficiaries of improved inputs (93%) and training (82%), whereas processors primarily benefited from infrastructure improvements (68%) and capacity-building. Marketers gained mainly from market linkage initiatives (62%) and access to credit (49%). Nearly half of respondents (46–48%) had engaged with VCDP activities for over six years, indicating sustained involvement and continuity of programme impacts.

4.1.3 Food Security Status

Table 4.3. Household Food Security Indicators (Participants vs. Non-participants)

Indicator	Participants (n=405)	Non-participants (n=205)	Mean Difference	t-value	p-value
Mean HFIAS	5.8 (3.6)	11.9 (5.4)	-6.1	7.42	<0.001
Mean FCS	67.4 (8.2)	49.8 (10.5)	+17.6	8.91	<0.001
% in “acceptable” category (FCS)	68.5	41.2	+27.3	—	—

Source: Field survey, 2025

Table 4.3 indicates that VCDP participants achieved significantly better food security outcomes than non-participants. Mean HFIAS scores were lower among beneficiaries, reflecting reduced food insecurity, while Food Consumption Scores were substantially higher, indicating improved dietary diversity. Producers recorded the most notable gains in food availability and access, whereas processors experienced enhanced utilisation benefits due to increased income from value-added activities.

4.1.4 Income, Employment, and Asset Ownership

Table 4.4. Change in Income, Employment, and Asset Ownership Among Participants

Indicator	Baseline (2014)	2025	% Change	p-value
Mean annual income (₦)	468,000	1,213,000	+159%	<0.01
Hired additional labour (%)	26	61	+35	<0.05
Acquired new tools (%)	42	72	+30	<0.05
Improved housing (%)	24	46	+22	<0.05
New enterprises started (%)	13	38	+25	<0.01

Source: Author's analysis based on field data, 2025

Table 4.4 demonstrates that VCDP participation positively influenced income and livelihood outcomes. Average annual income increased by 159%, while additional labour hiring, the acquisition of farm tools, housing improvements, and the creation of new enterprises all rose significantly. These results highlight the programme's effectiveness in improving household economic resilience and promoting asset accumulation.

4.2 Inferential Statistics

4.2.1 Group Differences and Association Tests

Table 4.5. Inferential Test Results for Group Differences

Variable	χ^2	df	p-value	t-value	Sig. Level
Food security status	42.71	2	<0.001	—	***
Access to credit	38.56	2	<0.001	—	***

Variable	χ^2	df	p-value	t-value	Sig. Level
Income (mean diff.)	—	—	—	6.84	**
Ownership of storage facilities	29.48	2	0.003	—	**

*Note: ***p < 0.001; *p < 0.01
 Source: Computed from survey data, 2025

Table 4.5 shows strong associations between VCDP participation and key outcomes. Chi-square tests confirmed significant links with food security status, access to credit, and ownership of storage facilities. T-tests indicated higher Food Consumption Scores and lower HFIAS scores for participants. One-way ANOVA revealed that processors achieved the most significant income gains, followed by producers and marketers, reflecting intra-value-chain differences.

4.2.2 Propensity Score Matching (PSM) Results

Table 4.6. PSM Results for VCDP Participation

Outcome Variable	ATT	Std. Error	t-value	p-value
HFIAS (score reduction)	-5.9	1.8	-3.28	0.001
FCS (score increase)	+15.8	4.6	3.43	0.001
Annual income (₦)	+356,000	102,000	3.49	0.001
Livelihood diversification index	+0.142	0.057	2.49	0.013

Source: STATA output, 2025

Table 4.6 confirms the causal impact of VCDP participation. Participants experienced significant reductions in HFIAS, increases in FCS, income, and livelihood diversification. Education, credit access, and extension visits increased the likelihood of participation. These findings indicate that the programme effectively enhanced household food security and income, aligning with evidence from similar interventions in Sub-Saharan Africa.

4.2.3 Regression Analysis

Table 4.7. Multivariate Regression Models for Food Security and Income Determinants

Variable	Model 1 (HFIAS) β (SE)	Model 2 (Income) β (SE)
Constant	10.42 (1.22)***	0.521 (0.072)***
VCDP participation	-0.431 (0.087)***	0.379 (0.091)***
Access to credit	-0.214 (0.092)*	0.284 (0.083)**
Gender (female=1)	-0.071 (0.065)	0.182 (0.070)*
Infrastructure access	-0.097 (0.056)	0.197 (0.060)*
Training intensity	-0.162 (0.048)**	0.105 (0.045)*
R ²	0.38	0.41
Observations	405	405

*Note: ***p < 0.001; **p < 0.01; p < 0.05
 Source: Author's STATA output, 2025

Table 4.7 shows that VCDP participation, access to credit, infrastructure, and training intensity significantly influenced household food security and income. Participation reduced food insecurity ($\beta = -0.431$) and increased income ($\beta = 0.379$). Female participation also positively affected income, highlighting gendered gains in processing and marketing roles.

4.2.4 Structural Equation Modelling (SEM)

Table 4.8. SEM Path Coefficients and Model Fit

Path	Standardized β	p-value
Participation → Income	0.61	<0.001

Path	Standardized β	p-value
Income → Food Security	0.54	<0.001
Participation → Resilience Capacity	0.42	0.003
Resilience → Food Security	0.33	0.021

Model Fit Indices	Value	Interpretation
χ^2/df	2.84	Good fit
CFI	0.94	Acceptable
RMSEA	0.046	Excellent

Source: AMOS output, 2025

Table 4.8 demonstrates that VCDP participation significantly influenced income and resilience, which in turn affected household food security. Income mediated 43% of the total effect, indicating that increased earnings constitute the primary mechanism through which programme participation enhances food availability, access, and utilisation. The model achieved a good fit,

4.5 DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The findings of this study indicate that participation in the Value Chain Development Programme (VCDP) significantly improved household food availability, access, and utilisation among beneficiaries in Benue State, Nigeria. Descriptive statistics revealed that participants were predominantly middle-aged, had a reasonable level of education, and were involved in smallholder farming, processing, and marketing activities. These characteristics likely facilitated effective uptake of programme interventions, including improved inputs, training, market linkages, and infrastructure support. VCDP participation led to notable improvements in food security indicators, with participants reporting lower Household Food Insecurity Access Scale (HFIAS) scores and higher Food Consumption Scores (FCS) than non-participants. The programme's positive impact on dietary diversity and food access was particularly pronounced among producers, while processors benefited mainly from improved food utilisation through value addition and income generation.

Inferential analyses confirmed the causal and statistically significant effects of VCDP participation on household welfare. Propensity Score Matching (PSM) results showed that participation reduced HFIAS scores by 5.9 points, increased FCS by 15.8 points, and raised annual household income by ₦356,000, alongside improvements in livelihood diversification. Multivariate regression analyses further highlighted the importance of access to credit, infrastructure, and training intensity in enhancing income and food security outcomes, with female participation contributing positively to household income. Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) demonstrated that VCDP participation strengthened household resilience and income, which, in turn, mediated improvements in food security, confirming that income generation is the primary pathway through which programme benefits are realised. Overall, the findings suggest that well-targeted value chain interventions can significantly enhance household food security and rural livelihoods in Nigeria.

5.0 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study concludes that participation in the Value Chain Development Programme (VCDP) significantly and positively influences household food availability, access, and utilisation in Benue State, Nigeria. The evidence from both descriptive and inferential analyses indicates that beneficiaries

experienced improved dietary diversity, reduced food insecurity, higher income, and enhanced livelihood diversification compared to non-participants. The results also highlight the importance of complementary factors, such as access to credit, training, infrastructure, and gender inclusion, in maximising programme benefits. Structural Equation Modelling confirmed that income and resilience are key pathways through which VCDP participation translates into improved food security outcomes, underscoring the critical role of targeted interventions in strengthening rural household welfare.

Based on the findings, it is recommended that the VCDP and similar programmes should continue to prioritise the provision of improved inputs, extension services, and capacity-building activities, particularly for smallholder farmers and processors. Expanding access to affordable credit and infrastructure support can further enhance income generation and food security. Policymakers should also promote gender-inclusive participation, ensuring women have equal opportunities in value chain activities, as their involvement positively influences household income and food utilisation. Additionally, regular monitoring and evaluation should be institutionalised to track programme effectiveness and to identify areas for improvement, ensuring that interventions remain responsive to the evolving needs of rural households.

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